

KIDS DIGITAL LIVES IN CoVID-19 TIMES

*DIGITAL PRACTICES, SAFETY AND WELL-BEING
OF THE 6-12 YEARS OLD*

A qualitative study - National report - ITALY

Lorenzo Giuseppe Zaffaroni
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Milano
lorenzogiuseppe.zaffaroni@unicatt.it

Davide Cino
Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Milano
davide.cino@unicatt.it

UNIVERSITÀ CATTOLICA del Sacro Cuore

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I. Executive summary

I.I. Key findings

Here we report the main findings from the interviews with 5 families with different SES (see the methodological section for more information about the sample). The results show the main transformations that occurred with the arrival of the lockdown, referring in particular to online activities, parental mediation, families' and children's attitudes towards technology, and children's school activities.

- All the interviewed families reported having quite a few digital devices at home even before the lockdown, although some families were more media-rich than others.
- Children's time spent with digital technologies increased during the lockdown, mostly because of educational activities, but also for social activities.
- Children engaged in three main digital activities: educational, social, and entertainment.
- While some children faced some difficulties in doing certain activities due to limited digital skills, most of them learned a fair deal of new ones, especially concerning educational activities. This was particularly true for younger kids.
- Neither the children nor their parents were particularly happy with remote schooling.
- To supplement the few devices available, some families had to buy new devices, or get broadband connectivity.
- Rules about screen time were relaxed during the lockdown, since marking clear-cut lines was not possible, nor desirable according to parents.
- Most families reported positive attitudes towards digital technology, especially concerning educational activities, and manifested the ability to navigate the media ecosystem in their homes.
- The increased use and reliance on digital devices led to some changes in terms of the number of devices, use patterns, and mediation rules.
- While the lockdown did not affect the families' attitudes towards digital technologies, most of the families became more aware of the fundamental role of technologies in enabling remote schooling activities.
- Both children and parents reported positive attitudes about technology use during the lockdown: the former because it would make them feel less alone, the latter as a source of support to keep their children busy.
- In some families, the lockdown represented an opportunity for family media time together.
- Neither the parents nor their children reported encountering more online risks despite the increased time spent online.

I.II. Recommendations

Building on the results of the study, several needs were revealed. The main findings reveal that households have equal access to digital technology and connectivity at home, and that investments must be made to ensure that all households are covered by internet connectivity. Consequently, we specify the following recommendations:

- The national government needs to make sure all families have equal access to digital technology and connectivity at home, to minimise school drop-out.
- Interventions should be planned with teachers and educators to implement remote schooling activities.
- While children were able to acquire new digital skills on their own, the circumstances show how pivotal it is to better educate youth to use digital technology to the best of their potential.
- Parents should not be held accountable for their ability to assist their children with remote schooling, since they may lack both the time and the skills to do so.
- Investments should enable that all households are covered by internet connectivity and possess proper digital equipment so that both parents, children and teachers have the right digital skills for unexpected circumstances.
- It is extremely important to minimize negative impacts of lack of in-presence schooling and increase of technology use.

1. Introduction

KiDiCoTi - A JRC coordinated study on the impacts of the COVID-19 crisis on Children's use of digital technology, online safety and well-being

During the unprecedented first wave of the COVID-19 crisis (Spring 2020), most of the children in Europe (and beyond) experienced a lock-down at home. Schooling, leisure time, and social contacts have taken place at home and at least sometimes via digital media. Consequently, children became more involved in digital media and at the same time more often the audience of digital content. We indeed expect that the more children spend online, the more online risks increase (such as encountering inappropriate content, overuse, commercial pressure, unwanted contact, cyberbullying, physical and mental health impact, etc.), but also that the situation opens them to new opportunities (education, engagement, political participation, creativity, community involvement, etc.).

To draw an image of the threat landscape in the home context, mitigate those risks and support the positive externalities of this unexpected crisis, the international team coordinated by the JRC started gathering comparable cross-national data: qualitative via interviews and quantitative via a representative sample. This report aims to present the interview-based results. The goal of the study is to inform stakeholders of the current trends and possible impacts of the COVID-19 crisis on children's use of digital technology, online safety, privacy and well-being at home. The analysis maps the evolution of children's digital engagement in times of the COVID-19 Crisis (first wave in spring and after, envisaging a longitudinal study with a broader sample) with a particular focus on children's online safety, privacy and well-being.

A cross-European research network has facilitated this effort with 26 research centres in 17 European countries and the research office of UNICEF collaborating on this study. It has also benefited from the synergies established with the Joint Research Center of European Commission (EC) (JRC.B.4 - Human Capital and Employment) and the interest and support of the Directorate-General of the EC (CNECT.DDG2.G.3.001).

Research Questions

1. How do children age 6-12 years old engage with digital technologies during this specific time in the interviewed families?
2. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's behaviour and activities related to technologies?
3. What are the children and parent's attitudes towards digital technology use and online activities during the lock-down?
4. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's attitudes towards digital technology and online activities? How do parents perceive the associated risks and opportunities?
5. What impacts for the future?

1. Methodology

Kids Digital Lives in COVID-19 Times (KiDiCoTi) is a research project on how children and parents engaged with digital technologies during the lockdown period in Europe. Overall, a qualitative study with semi-structured interviews as well as a quantitative survey were conducted. The main question concerned how digital media are used by children and their parents in the context of remote schooling, leisure time and the management of (distant) social contacts. The project also aimed to understand whether and how these experiences may have had an impact on the overall family well-being as well as the online safety of children. The research project was coordinated by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission under the lead of Stephane Chaudron.

Adding to the findings of the quantitative survey (Vuorikari et al., 2020), this report focuses on qualitative data collected within the European project. This study has been conducted in 15 countries (Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Denmark, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Switzerland). The research tools (interview guide for children and parents, pre-interview questionnaire for parents, time capsule for children) were carefully developed by the international research team.

Specifically, in this work we will report on findings from the Italian qualitative study only, where five families with children aged 6-12 were interviewed. When visiting families, the researchers maintained social distance and took all the necessary precautions.

2.1. Procedure

In this section, the implementation of the study in Italy is discussed. For a general overview of the protocol of observations and the protocol of analysis that were shared across participating research groups, we refer to these specific documents.

2.2. The sampling procedure

To contact families of interest the research team first discussed recruiting strategies to reach a sample as diverse as possible in terms of children's and parents' age and families' socioeconomic status. As such, following a purposive sampling approach, a total of five families – with SES ranging from low to high – were involved in the study, interviewing 5 mothers and 5 children (three girls and two boys) from North Italy, four from Lombardia and one from Emilia-Romagna.

Families were first contacted to be informed about the nature and scope of the study, addressing doubts and questions, and explaining the relevant ethical guidelines adopted. Families were then provided with the pre-interview materials (a survey for parents and a time capsule for children, aimed at creatively and expressively collecting their interpretations and emotions about the lockdown experience), which was then sent back to the researchers before the interviews took place.

Interviews were scheduled according to families' needs and preferences, and were conducted in June 2020.

2.3. The sample

Below we report on the sample's background information. Specifically, we indicate an identifying number for the family (i.e. IT1, IT2, etc.), fantasy name, and demographic information about the interviewees.

Family	Interviewees	Geographic area	SES
IT1	Alessandra, mother, 40 (IT04m40) Riccardo, son, 8 (IT04b8)	Milano-Marittima, Emilia-Romagna, IT	High
IT2	Chiara, mother, 36 (IT02m36) Marta, daughter, 6 (IT02g6)	Milano, Lombardia, Italy	Medium
IT3	Elisa, mother, 49 (IT03m42) Anna, daughter, 9 (IT03g9)	Milano, Lombardia, Italy	Medium
IT4	Margherita, mother, 43 (IT01m43) Bruno, son, 6 (IT01b6)	Milano, Lombardia, Italy	High
IT5	Isabel, mother, 49 (IT05m49) Sofia, daughter, 12 (IT05g12)	Milano, Lombardia, Italy	Low

2.4. Implementation of the protocol of observations

Out of 5 interviews, 4 were conducted face to face in June 2020. The duration varied from 30 minutes to one hour. In every family, we interviewed a parent and the child, except in one where both parents were interviewed. Normally, the parent was present during the children's interviews and the children left the setting after his or her interview. However, in two families, the daughters decided to follow the mother's interview.

Before beginning the interviews, all researchers explained the scope of the research, discussed the informed consent forms along with privacy issues, and provided all the useful information before asking the interviewees for their signatures.

After this, the interview structure followed the guidelines established by the European team:

Child interview (20-30 min)

The interviews started with an ice breaker conversation about the activity booklet and the time capsule. The interview guide then covered the use of technology, remote schooling, parental mediation concerning media, entertainment, wellbeing, concerns about digital media and lock-down

Parent interview (20-30 min)

The interviews started with ice-breaker questions about the lockdown experience, when necessary. All interviews covered the various aims of the study, such as:

- general competences and practices with digital media and general use of technology;

- remote schooling;
- parental mediation concerning media, entertainment, wellbeing;
- concerns regarding digital media and the lockdown period;
- risks and benefits associated with using digital media;
- relationships between digital media practices and family configurations;
- rules and parental mediation;
- perspectives on future use in the light of current events.

Acknowledgements to the family (2 min)

Face to face interviews were recorded using the interviewer's smartphone or digital recorder. The audio was then saved to a local drive or a cloud drive, both with password protection.

Shortly after every interview, the interviewers filled out an observation minute to record relevant aspects which emerged during interviews about the family context to better understand the family situation.

2.5. Implementation of the protocol analysis

The interviewers assigned alias names and codes to both families and family members and transcribed the audio of the interviews verbatim. The coding of the interview data was conducted by following the coding scheme developed by the European team, using Excel and NVivo.

Family portraits were created both by drawing on interview notes and observational minutes, the documents provided by the families and the results of the first coding activity. The portraits hence reflect the contents of the interviews but contain further information about the family context that did not make it into the interview settings, or which were gathered beforehand.

The researchers conducted a thematic analysis based on the first round of coding and the preliminary comparisons between families. The codes that emerged from the analysis were then refined to provide detailed answers to the research questions of this study:

1. How do children age 6-12 years old engage with digital technologies during this specific time in the interviewed families?
2. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's behaviour and activities related to technologies?
3. What are the children and parent's attitudes towards digital technology use and online activities during the lock-down?
4. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's attitudes towards digital technology and online activities? How do parents perceive the associated risks and opportunities?
5. What impact for the future?

2.6. Discussion of methodology

The sampling process aimed to gather families that were heterogeneous concerning SES, family structure and urban/suburban location. Although it cannot be said that our sampling process is representative, the chosen families well represent the diverse arrangements and familial context that faced the pandemic.

Our qualitative approach, combined with the research questions and probes provided by the European team proved to be apt for this study. The friendly and intimate setting that accompanied the interview process was particularly important in providing participants with a relaxed mood that aided in gathering trustworthy answers.

3. Country portrait in COVID-19 times

We provide a summary section reporting on the main events related to the COVID-19 crisis at the national level. We feel it is important to provide contextual information to situate the qualitative data from the interviews in the broader Italian context.

The first cases

Medical authorities reported the first confirmed case of Covid-19 in Italy on the 17th of February 2020. The case involved a man from the province of Lodi who arrived at the Codogno hospital with flu-like symptoms. As his condition worsened, he tested positive for COVID-19, as did, shortly afterwards, his pregnant wife and a friend. Sixteen more cases were confirmed on the 20th of February. Among them was the first reported Covid-19 patient to die. The number of cases subsequently rose to 152 by February 22. As of March 2, 2020, all Italian regions reported at least one case of infection, and by the 18th of March one positive case for the coronavirus was found in every Italian province. On the following day, 3 March 2020, 3089 cases were confirmed in Italy and deaths exceeded hundreds.

From the 5th of March, classroom teaching was suspended for all schools and universities. On the 9th of March, the government designated Italy as a unique “protected zone” and suspended teaching activities throughout the country until the 3rd of April. In the following ordinance, on April 10, the school activities were suspended until May 3. However, already on April 8, the Minister of Health forced the Minister of Education to declare the end of the school year, postponing the reopening of schools until September.

The national lockdown

On March 9, the Prime Minister issued a new Presidential Decree (DPCM) which extended the travel ban for unnecessary reasons, the suspension of all sports, exhibitions and events, museum closures along cultural sites throughout Italy. Two days later, on March 11, commercial and retail activities were also closed, except for ‘essential’ services: food shops, pharmacies and para pharmacies. A further decree prohibited all individuals from moving or travelling via public or private transport in any municipality except for proven work requirements, absolute urgency or health reasons. The government repeatedly extended such measures until the 3rd of May.

Reduction of containment measures

As the infection curve dropped as a result of the restrictive measures adopted, a new decree – taking effect on May 4 – relaxed the containment measures. Citizens were allowed to travel to visit relatives (within the regional territory), public parks were reopened and various productive activities resumed. On the 18th of May, businesses, museums, bars, restaurants, hairdressers and beauty centres reopened throughout Italy, and religious celebrations were allowed. On the 25th of May, sports centres reopened and from June 3 free movement between regions was allowed.

Postponement of school openings

Classroom attendance was set to be resumed in the following school year (2020-2021). However, since the 4th of May, some universities allowed exams on-site as well as final exams and others shifted to remote activities, while secondary school exams still operated remotely. The Ministry of Education determined that students can be admitted to the following school year even with more than one failed class, granted that they would undergo recovery courses at the beginning of the following school year. However, students who were considered unable to succeed the school year – based on the results of school attendance before the lockdown – were considered unapt to pass the year.

Containment measures after the first lockdown (June-October)

Another decree, which came into force on the 15th of June, further reduced the restraint measures, providing for the reopening of gambling and betting halls, theatres and cinemas, as well as cultural and social venues.

While the in-person teaching suspension remained in place, the new decree added the possibility for universities to reopen their libraries. Furthermore, universities were allowed to conduct internships, seminars, research, experimental and teaching laboratory activities and exercises. However, the decree established these activities must also be provided remotely.

Schools, on the other hand, were allowed to provide their facilities for non-school and non-formal recreational and educational activities, with the help of qualified staff. The decree left it open to the regions to decide whether to use their facilities.

It was also established that from September 2020, with the opening of the new school year, classroom teaching would be resumed, provided that several conditions were met. To reduce the risk of infection, school staff were able to undergo a serological test. Schools were required to provide an alternative curriculum for any distance learning in case of temporary closure or episodic quarantine.

Second wave and new restrictive measures

With the increase of the number of infections, reaching 3678 cases on October 7, the Prime Minister confirmed the previously established measures with a new decree-law (in force since the 8th of October). In addition, the state of emergency has been extended until the 31st of January 2021. The regions were allowed to increase the restrictive measures, but not to loosen them.

As for schools, the October 24 decree established that high schools can organise remote activities complementary to the co-present activities. Universities were required to adapt their organisation to the epidemiological condition of their territory.

A further decree, in force from October 26 until the end of November, added new restrictions, such as curfews in several Italian regions with higher risks. Part of this new decree again focused on distance learning, providing for an increase in digital teaching for secondary schools.

In response to the restrictive measures established during this period, a series of protests broke out in several Italian cities, where the citizens most affected by the new measures demanded financial compensation for the recent restrictions.

Differentiated risk reduction scenarios

The Prime Ministerial Decree on the 3rd of November 2020 ordered a national curfew from 22.00 to 5.00, extended until 15 January. The decree also required shopping centres to close on weekends and requires remote learning for high schools and secondary schools.

In addition, the Italian regions were grouped into three different scenarios of "epidemiological risk". In the regions (or parts of them) advanced to "scenario 2" and "scenario 3", also known as "yellow zones" and "orange zones", schools remained active until the eighth grade. In the regions (or parts of them) also known as "red zones", distance learning was introduced from the seventh grade. A decree-law of 2 December also imposed travel restrictions over the Christmas holiday period, specifically from the 21st of December 2020 to the 6th of January 2021.

Finally, middle and high school class attendance were expected to be blended as of the 25th of January 2021, with at least 75% of students in attendance.

Third-wave

As further extension of the state of emergency were previously established (on the 13th of January) until 30 April 2021, high schools were required to provide in-person teaching with at least 50% of students participating, up to a maximum of 75%, except for the 'red' areas.

These measures were extended until 6 April 2021 by a Prime Ministerial Decree on the 2nd of March. Schools of all levels would be closed in red zones and in areas where a set limit of infections is exceeded.

On April 17, the Prime Minister announced several reopenings of both commercial and noncommercial activities. As for schools, the yellow areas are expected to be fully open, while the orange and red areas are expected to allow only 50% of attending students.

(End of updates on April 19, 2021)

4. Family Portrait Gallery

Family IT1

Emilia-Romagna, Italy, small town

Face-to-face interview

June 20, 2020

Family members

- Alessandra, mother, 40 (IT04m40)
- Riccardo, son, 8 (IT04b8)

Context:

The family lives in a small town in Emilia-Romagna. The mother, a 40-year-old divorced woman who works as a doctor, spent a great deal of time working at a hospital in a COVID-19 ward during the lockdown. During this hard time the son – an 8-year-old – stayed at his grandparents' house with them, his mom and an uncle. While the mother would go back there to sleep at night, she stayed in a separate area of the house so as not to pose a risk to her family members. The house has a shared garden where the child could spend some of his leisure time.

Technology is an important part of Riccardo's life. He describes himself as very passionate about his tablet, which he has been using extensively even before the lockdown. Even though the family owns a TV, a smartphone and a computer, he is not allowed to use them, nor seems particularly interested in doing so. As for the tablet, this is mainly used to play games, an activity his mother tries to control with some domestic rules, such as the "four-games-only rule". According to her tenet, Riccardo is only allowed to have four games on his tablet, so that he can – as in his words – "enjoy them fully", and uninstall one or more of them to install new ones, but always respecting this number.

Despite these attempts to regulate his son's technology use, Alessandra believes technology is a "life-saver", and that the tool is not good or bad per se, but it depends on how you use it. She also recognizes that, being a regular technology user herself, she cannot expect her son to act extremely differently, because – as in her words – "the apple doesn't fall far from the tree".

Both Riccardo and his mother believe the child's technology use increased during the lockdown, most of all because of online classes and homework. Riccardo doesn't seem to have strong feelings about the whole remote-schooling experience. Apart from lamenting the amount of homework he had to do at the beginning, he encountered no difficulties in learning how to use the educational apps provided by the school – which he describes as "very easy". In turn, he appreciated the opportunity to stop the video during a class to stretch his legs a little bit. What seemed to be most impacted by the lockdown concerning technology was, in turn, his social life. Attending his dance classes was "boring" online and being in front of a screen even to have fun caused him a little video call fatigue, which sometimes led him to turn his camera off and leave the room while he was practising with his dance teacher.

Video calls allowed him to stay in touch with his best friend as well. However, he recounted how strange it was to adjust their interactions to the online environment at the beginning and then, when they finally met in person after the lockdown, to adjust them back. In telling so, he reported feeling a little embarrassed because "after talking to each other on video when we were finally together [in person] we did not know what to do". In the span of a single afternoon, however, the children overcame their disorientation and started playing together like they always did.

Alessandra doesn't have very positive feelings about the remote-schooling experience, which she found to be very little interactive and difficult to manage, not only for her child but for herself as well. This situation, however, was exacerbated by a demanding job that asked her to spend a great deal of time far from home, and not to have close contact with her son during the toughest time of the lockdown – during which Riccardo seemed sad and confused about the whole situation. It was in this dark period, however, that she came up with a creative digital idea: asking her son to recount his feelings on a video diary, an activity he was very happy to engage in. Such a task was, in her words, very useful for the child to reconnect with his feelings, and effective because “he stopped doing it when things slowly got back to normal”, as he was less stressed out.

When the lockdown's restriction loosened up, Riccardo started spending some of his time with his father's family as well, specifically his grandparents, where – however – due to different digital orientations, he is not allowed to use his tablet at all. Such a restriction seems to be, in his mothers' words, a little tough for the child, who cannot wait to go back to his mother's to use his tablet again at the end of the week.

Overall, Alessandra and Riccardo benefited from technology use during this tough time. Even though this caused some problems, cons were balanced out by the many pros technology came with, not least the opportunity to keep the child engaged in something he likes, and which his mom is not afraid to encourage, with due limits.

ILLUSTRATIVE QUOTE

When my best friend and I met in person again after the lockdown we were a little embarrassed. We got used to seeing each other on video and we couldn't come up with anything to do in person at first.

Riccardo, son, 8, (IT04b8)

Family IT2

Milan, Italy, big town

Face-to-face interview

June 26, 2020

ILLUSTRATIVE QUOTE

The paradox is that Marta was very precise in doing her homework, but I forgot to send it to the teachers, do you know what I mean?

Chiara, mother, 36 (IT02m36)

Family members

- Chiara, mother, 36 (IT02m36)
- Marta, daughter, 6 (IT02g6)
- Luca, father, 50 (IT02f50)

Context

The family lives in an urban area in Milan, in an apartment building. Both parents have university degrees. The mother, a 36-year-old woman, has two jobs: she works full-time for a humanitarian NGO and part-time in a community centre that she co-founded with her husband. The father, a 50-year-old man, works in the same community centre as a manager. As a result of the lockdown, the mother's work for the NGO increased. In contrast, the father's work was reconverted, as the community centre became a home meal delivery facility for the COVID-19 emergency. For this reason, both parents were very busy during the lockdown and spent a lot of time away from home.

During this time, the 6-year-old daughter followed her mother and father during work shifts and spent the rest of the time at home, when her mother would do remote work. Sometimes, the daughter would also spend her leisure time outside in the communal garden of their apartment building.

Marta is fascinated by technology and, having recently learned to read, is now beginning to explore increasingly complex functions. As the lockdown began, she spent more time with technology and engaged with new activities alongside traditional ones. Marta mainly used on-demand streaming platforms and her mother's computer. Sometimes, Marta would grab her mother's smartphone to play games. Watching movies is the only communal activity of the family, while Marta's use of the computer is autonomous. On the computer, Marta only carries out activities on websites for children that her mother suggested to her.

Marta's mother does identify as a restrictive parent, but recognizes that she always has to keep "one eye open" to monitor her daughter's online activity. The rules on technology use have not changed significantly during the lockdown. Marta is allowed to make autonomous use of streaming platforms and computers with soft time restrictions, but she is often denied the use of her mother's smartphone. The prohibition concerns the fact that the smartphones in the family are used for work, and thus are "personal" devices.

The lockdown represented an opportunity to introduce new technology practices within the family, especially in the sphere of interpersonal communication. Marta has developed a new game mode based on video communication. Specifically, she used video calls and screen recording to "stage" movie scenes with her cousin and grandparents.

Remote schooling has been a great challenge for the family. Marta found the online lessons uninteresting and encountered several difficulties. Besides, connectivity problems and managing interactions online represented the biggest obstacle. In particular, homework

assignment was a very complex procedure that was complicated by the lack of digital skills in the hands of teachers.

The mother equally reported negative opinions about remote schooling. In particular, Chiara reported difficulties in “managing” the activities that Marta would otherwise carry out independently before the lockdown. Remote schooling required greater parental involvement, and, in Chiara's case, this was a source of stress. Chiara is a mother who believes in empowering her daughter in the school context. Independence is a key value in her approach to parenting. However, this was incompatible with the demands of the teachers, who requested constant communication with parents to facilitate remote schooling.

Although the mother does not make extensive use of technology, she has positive opinions about it. Chiara considers the development of digital skills and autonomy as an important factor. At the same time, the mother does not frame technology as a central aspect in the overall development of her child. In this regard, the mother's only preoccupation with technology concerns future occurrences of remote schooling.

Family IT3

Milan, Italy, big town

Face-to-face interview

June 25, 2020

Family members

- Elisa, mother, 49 (IT03m42)
- Anna, daughter, 9 (IT03g9)
- Francesco, 45 (IT03f45)

ILLUSTRATIVE QUOTE

Using technology made me feel less sad because it would distract me and keep me busy so that I would not think about the whole situation

Anna, daughter, 9 (IT03g9)

Context

Anna is a 9-year-old girl who, like her peers, found herself dealing with new and unprecedented circumstances she had no experience of. This occurrence, in her words, made her feel sad and worried. She feared her family could get infected, and her anxiety was partly fueled by watching the news on television, to the point where she started “hating watching it”, because all she could hear concerned the pandemic. Watching cartoons, however, helped her soothe her fears.

In this period, technology played a huge part in her and her family’s life. Her technology use unsurprisingly increased, due to a lot of educational, social and creative activities she engaged in. The remote school experience was challenging for her, as she missed going to school a lot, as well as meeting her friends and teachers. Online classes were difficult to follow in her words, especially because she could not rely on a physical blackboard where the teacher would jot down important notes and information to remember. Due to the lockdown measures, she was also forced to attend their guitar classes online, something she described as “weird” since she no longer had the opportunity to play her instrument with her mates, but on a one-on-one tutoring session.

Despite such hard feelings, using technology proved useful to her: before the Covid crisis she did not even know how to turn a computer on, nor to engage in any sort of activity. Familiarizing with the device, in turn, allowed her to learn new things, such as watching video tutorials. This activity is something she became particularly fond of, since she discovered to be passionate about origami, an activity she engaged in very frequently. Thanks to her smartphone and computer she was also able to have some social experiences, such as celebrating her friends’ birthdays on Zoom, or video calling her friends to play and do origami together. She also learned to use Alexa, a smart speaker “not so smart” according to her, since she would sometimes fail to select the music she likes. In her words, technology helped her feel less sad because it would keep her busy and able to stay in touch with her friends.

Her mother, Elisa, recognizes the changes that COVID-19 caused in her daughter’s technology use. From buying coincidentally a smart TV, to adopt broadband internet connection in the house (as until that day they would only use the internet from their mobile phone because they did not need it), to acquiring Alexa so to distract her daughter from the whole situation, the pandemic changed the media ecology of her house. Elisa believes that technology use increased a lot in this period: in her words, her computer was “full of dust” since nobody would use it before. She does not see such an increase as a cause of conflict in her family, but in turn thinks technology helped them manage the situation. While using specific mediation rules was not deemed necessary, she still tried to make sure her daughter would use media properly according to the family’s values, especially in terms of contents.

Not very passionate about technology, Elisa thinks that her daughter had the opportunity to learn new important digital skills in this period, even though if it wasn't for the pandemic, she thinks she did not need to learn them all now but even later in life. While she did not express strong feelings about the remote schooling experience, she does believe the apps provided by the schools were not good enough for educational purposes, so that both she and her daughter were very glad to get rid of them at the end of school year.

Overall, despite mixed feelings about the unprecedented circumstances and the incorporation and use of old and new devices, digital media seemed to have helped to ease a tough moment that was taking a toll on the child, while also hastening a digitalization of the domestic environment that helped Anna acquire new digital skills whose importance her mother recognizes and values.

Family IT4

Metropolitan Area of Milan

Face-to-face interview

June 20, 2020.

Family members

- Margherita, mother, 43 (IT4m43)
- Bruno, son, 6 (IT4b6)

ILLUSTRATIVE QUOTE

With distance learning, [I experienced] a lot of discomforts. At least in my case, [the children] were not at all self-sufficient, so the time of distance learning was a moment of total personal commitment as my husband had to be with the younger child.

Margherita, mother, 43 years old (IT4m43)

Context

Bruno is a lively child who grew up in a family where technology is well accepted: his mother develops digital technologies for cultural events and recognises the important value of technology – both as a working tool and as a form of 'edutainment'.

Bruno suffered the lockdown for the same reasons as the other participants in the research: it was difficult for him to give up seeing his friends and grandparents in person, and distance learning was a particularly difficult challenge also because of his age.

Bruno's main activities with technology did not change radically during the lockdown, but they certainly saw an increase. In particular, Bruno started watching more television through streaming platforms, as the family bought a subscription to the Disney Plus platform. Computer use has increased both because of distance learning and because Bruno himself has started asking his parents to guide him in his online navigation to game-learning sites of his interest – which were often suggested by the teacher in class.

While technology (especially video calls) represented a resource – allowing Bruno to video call his grandparents and “meet” them – it still complicated Bruno's learning. The video lessons had frequent connectivity problems and the platforms used to run them (Google Meet and Zoom) required the presence and active participation of parents. Despite her high level of digital literacy, his mother Margherita also confessed to having difficulties in managing these platforms, which she did not use in her work before the lockdown.

The house rules for consuming digital technologies did not change during the lockdown, nor did parents' opinions. Margherita, Bruno's mother, however, pointed out that the use of distance learning posed a great challenge in terms of family organisation: very often her son was demotivated to follow lessons and was often distracted, requiring her presence although she was often already busy working. Digital technology, especially television, therefore represented a tool for managing family leisure and working times.

In addition, the mother emphasises the importance of providing her son with less "passive" play and learning practices available on the Internet, and hence denounces the shared rhetoric that technology is 'right all round'. Her opinion emerges as it was not easy for her to find sufficiently interactive and learning content for her son.

Family IT5

Milan, Italy, big town

Face-to-face interview

June 23, 2020

Family members

- Isabel, mother, 49 (IT5m49)
- Sofia, daughter, 12 (IT5g12)

Context

Sofia, a 12-year-old girl, comes across as a shy and reserved girl who likes going to school. The experience of being in isolation has been a great challenge for Sofia, especially concerning distance learning, as she is not used to using a computer. Before the lockdown, the family's home computer seemed to her a 'decorative object' that did not operate particularly well. Hence, as the lockdown approached, her mother Isabel rushed to ask an acquaintance for help in getting her daughter a computer that could be used for distance learning.

Before the isolation, Sofia's technology use habits consisted of watching television and YouTube videos both on her Smart TV and on her mobile phone, which she has had since the beginning of lower secondary school (scuola media). Before the lockdown, Sofia already enjoyed YouTubers who played video games. With regard to school, Sofia was used to doing online research for her homework with the aid of her computer, but she transcribes her findings manually in her notebook. Communication with her "few friends" also took place in digital contexts before the lockdown, mainly on WhatsApp groups.

Once the lockdown began, Sofia started to develop her skills with digital technologies, in particular the computer and mobile phone. Despite initial difficulties, Sofia proved to be a quick learner, and particularly enjoyed the ability to conduct online research to complete the tasks assigned by her teachers.

Clearly, the isolation came as a big shock to Sofia's habits: used to getting up early and going to bed early, she now has more time, especially in the evenings, to browse the Internet. Online communication with friends has increased and has continued to take place mainly in WhatsApp groups – with and without the presence of adults. Sofia, who has a reserved character, finds it difficult to communicate within these environments where many of her classmates enjoy mocking teachers and other classmates by producing personalised WhatsApp "stickers" of their faces. Not agreeing with these practices, Sofia instead preferred to devote her time online to practising new activities: listening to music and dancing (in the company of her mother), assisting her mother (who, with her daughter's support, used YouTube extensively to learn new things), and doing other activities in the company of her family, such as watching TV.

Sofia's parents welcomed technology as a useful tool and particularly appreciated their daughter's ability to learn, as well as her newly acquired homework autonomy. Sofia's competence was also appreciated as her parents referred to her in case of technical problems. Sofia's mother did not impose any particular restrictions or rules on her daughter, based on her great trust in her. However, concerns about Internet use were not absent: the mother recognises the risks of digital technologies and reports that she once advised her daughter to 'block' interactions with strangers on Instagram that required access to her profile.

After the experience of the first lockdown, Sofia and her parents long for a return to “normality” – in particular, Sofia’s return to school – but consider the experience useful due to the new skills learned.

ILLUSTRATIVE QUOTE

We got [the computer] before the lockdown, but I didn't use it that much. So I didn't know how to use it, I didn't know how to download apps. ... Then over time, when I started doing these video lessons, I learned how to operate the computer and also the phone better. ... Now when I have to explain something to my mother I explain it to her. But then she doesn't understand!

Sofia, daughter, 12 years old (IT5g12)

5. Findings

5.1. How do children age 6-12 years old engage with digital technologies during this specific time in the interviewed families?

All the interviewed families reported having quite a few digital devices at home even before the lockdown, even though some families were more media-rich than others. Such a difference, however, was not related to their socio-economic status, but more to different use patterns. While some families did use a wide range of devices, others did not have a tv at all but, in turn, would use only smartphones and tablets.

Children's time spent with digital technologies increased during the lockdown, mostly because of educational activities, but also for social activities, such as keeping in touch with friends and relatives, playing games, doing sport, watching movies and, generally, leisure time. We found three main patterns of digital activities children engaged in: educational, social, and entertainment. Educational activities concern all the school-related tasks, such as attending online classes, doing homework, and using virtual didactic materials. Social activities encompass all those occurrences where children would use technology to foster their sociality with friends, grandparents, relatives, but also to take part in sports they could not attend in person (such as dance classes). Finally, entertainment activities cover all those circumstances where children would use digital technology to express themselves through digital storytelling, pictures, and video diaries, but also using technology to support and inform non-digital activities, such as learning how to prepare an origami, bake a cake, and the like. These activities need not be understood as mutually exclusive, since they could mingle and occur at the same time. For example, teachers could use their time online with children to propose creative activities within the virtual educational settings; a Skype call with friends or relatives, in turn, could become the occasion for children to create and record sketches, as recounted by a 6-year-old girl.

Overall, children learned a fair deal of new skills, especially concerning educational activities. This was particularly true for younger kids, while older peers were already more accustomed to using their computers for school purposes, or at least found familiarising with educational platforms easier, if not boring, to the point where a 9-year-old boy claimed that he "learned nothing new". All children, however, had to face the reality of learning how to be "at school" while being at home, even by facing technical difficulties that would take place even daily. Some children faced some difficulties in doing certain activities due to limited digital skills, such as a girl who did not know how to share her screen during a Skype call with her friends.

Children were not particularly happy with remote schooling, nor were their parents. The former mainly lamented the lack of sociality of such a measure, while the latter the excessive amount of domestic work that such a task would add. Several children reported to have felt sad about the lockdown, stressed out and sometimes overwhelmed by the situation. These feelings, however, were not in their words due to their use of digital technology, but mostly to the changed circumstances. Using technology, in turn, was seen as something positive since it would make children feel less alone and bored.

Parents as well appreciated using digital technology during the lockdown, since it would help them keep their children busy, giving them also the opportunity to talk with their friends and not miss out on sociality.

5.2. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's behaviour and activities related to technologies?

While technology per se was not a cause of concern and conflict within the domestic environment, the increased use and reliance on digital devices led to some changes in terms of the number of devices, use patterns, and mediation rules.

Some families had to buy new devices when only a few were already available or had to get broadband connectivity to allow all family members to navigate the web at the same time with a different device.

Rules about screen time tended to fade a little bit during the lockdown, since marking clear-cut lines was not possible, nor desirable according to parents. Overall, mediation strategies were dialogically adapted to the evolving situation more than exacerbated.

Some parents subscribed to streaming services such as Netflix, Disney Plus, or Spotify Premium, while others acquired new entertaining devices such as smart speakers, to create a more interactive digital environment and increase leisure opportunities within the household. Apart from this, both parents and children did not report significant changes concerning the type and quality of activities they engaged with using digital technology.

Due to the lockdown measures, parents had to spend more time with technology to foster their children's educational activities, even though this was true only at the beginning, or at least until children were not able to do everything on their own. Neither the parents, nor the children reported particular disruptions in their daily life due to technology, but they all recognised the intensity of use amplified, with some claiming that even if good, digital activities could not replace non-digital ones.

5.3. What are the children and parent's attitudes towards digital technology use and online activities during the lock-down?

Most families have positive attitudes towards digital technology and reportedly manifested their ability to navigate the media ecosystem in their homes. Positive attitudes in particular concern the learning and entertainment dimensions of digital technologies. Specifically, most parents show positive attitudes concerning the educational sphere: without digital technologies, their children would have not been able to partake in school activities and remote schooling. Furthermore, technologies provided Italian families with a source of “indoor” entertainment that complemented the lack of “outdoor” opportunities. In this respect, movies, games, and on-demand platforms fostered the “functioning” of family rhythms in the everyday experience of the lockdown.

The data show a positive association between the knowledge of digital technology held by parents and their attitudes towards such products and related activities. The more parents are used to adopting digital technologies in their work or daily life, the more they can evaluate them according to the positive impact they entail. In particular, high SES families are more prone to hold positive and constructive attitudes and opinions on technologies as a means of learning and intellectual stimuli. While parental mediation depends on the age of the children, it is most affected by parents' attitudes and parenting styles. Most parents allowed the use of digital devices during the lockdown and permitted more screen time than before. This choice is justified by reference to the changing family patterns and the more time spent "all together". All parents actively installed new learning apps, subscribed to on-demand platforms and other services, or acquired new devices during the lockdown period. As children actively manifested an increased interest in digital technologies and ventured into creative experiments by creating new media content (photos or videos), most parents encouraged this endeavour.

Familial restriction changed according to the fact that many children were allowed to use new devices during the lockdown. Extant permissions and rules (such as a fixed "TV time" per day) were not enforced as strictly as before, yet parents have not reportedly established new rules in advance, possibly because the lockdown was largely unexpected.

Some children became more acquainted with smartphones, tablets and laptops than before, mainly because of their daily investment in remote schooling. In some families, the lockdown represented an opportunity for increasing the time spent by the entire family, or by some of its members, using digital technologies together – for example, by watching movies together.

5.4. How did the lock-down disrupt or change the children's and family's attitudes towards digital technology and online activities? How do parents perceive the associated risks and opportunities?

While the lockdown did not affect the families' attitudes towards digital technologies, most of the families became more aware of the fundamental role of technologies in enabling remote schooling activities. Hence, most families recognised the usefulness of digital technologies for remote work and remote learning alike. As the interest in digital products (both for learning and entertainment) peaked in the lockdown period, most families discovered the resourcefulness of the Internet when it comes to learning resources, games, and other activities.

Almost all families reported that the lockdown period and remote schooling enabled their children to gain new competences concerning digital technologies. Learning to use video conference apps and learning platforms was welcomed as an important skill set that could help children also in the future.

Parents report that children acquired new opportunities in having more time to learn how to use digital technologies that could serve them later in life, such as videoconferencing and file sharing.

For one family, the increasing request to participate in their child's remote schooling activity was perceived as a burden that impacted both the parent's work schedule and the children's autonomy. This condition reflects the increased request for parental mediation when it comes to schooling activities, not only in respect to media access (i.e. laptop use), but also active participation in facilitating the submission of homework, solving connectivity issues and other technical problems. Experiences such as these undoubtedly shaped the parental perception of digital technologies and remote schooling as a possible source of problems.

Parents and children alike do not report having engaged with online risks despite the increased time spent online. This result is motivated by parents based on the fact that children's online activities through laptops, tablets and smartphones were often practised under parental supervision due to the increased proximity of family members during the lockdown. Parental supervision guaranteed children a higher degree of safety in respect to browsing safe and age-appropriate platforms and websites.

Finally, some parents are unsatisfied with the quality of remote schooling due to several reasons. For example, some parents perceived homework as too burdensome, while others criticised the learning modes that teachers adopted in remote schooling classes.

5.5. What impact for the future?

- Parents and children were both enthusiastic to slightly go back to normality as the lockdown measures started to progressively loosen up.
- Both parents and children wished they could start going to school in person. Parents reported feeling anxious at the idea of living in a similar situation again in the future, and children were eager to meet their teachers and classmates.
- Children generally did not report any particular activity they learned during the lockdown they would like to incorporate in their daily routine, even if some recognised that having the opportunity to video call a friend would allow them to overcome space boundaries when it is not possible to meet in person.
- Parents appreciated the role played by digital technology in this period and welcomed the idea of their children learning valuable skills for the future that could help them in life, beyond Covid-related challenging circumstances.

5.6. Surprising findings

- It is quite surprising to reckon how the families in our study were able to balance all the new stressful conditions provided by the pandemic into a liveable family context. This is particularly relevant in face of the seeming "unfamiliarity" of Italian families with digital technologies, remote work or smart working, as well as remote schooling.
- The response to the extremely uncertain lockdown period proves the resilience of Italian families and their proneness to embrace change. It is up to debate whether this condition will set the grounds for subsequent changes, such as policies and improvements in support of families and children to allow them to make the most out of these new lasting conditions.
- Yet, our results are only a partial representation of the condition of all Italian families. Hence, the analysis must take into account the families that were not

reached during this study and that do not possess the same SES and digital skills as the interviewed middle-class families do.

- Children showed a high degree of adaptability, creativity and imagination in respect to media use for entertainment and communicative purposes. For example, one child recounted that during the lockdown she used video conferencing tools (Zoom) to set up a “movie studio” where she could “film” movies with her cousin friend. The scenes were reportedly recorded via the recording function of the Zoom platform and were streamed to other family members. This example shows both the ability of children to navigate digital technologies and platforms, as well as their tendency to invent new creative and gaming activities based on their affordances.

6. Conclusions

The lockdown due to COVID-19 presented Italian families with unprecedented challenges. Children and parents had to readapt their daily routines completely since previous habits were disrupted. In this context, digital technology became an even more integral part of family life. While the interviewed families did not report drastic changes in terms of media use, they all recognised an increase in the time spent online by all family members, especially due to children’s educational activities and parents’ jobs.

The increase in screen time was welcomed positively, and no particular worries or fears were reported by our sample. This was mostly because using technology was pivotal during this difficult time.

Both children and parents, however, felt ill at ease with the whole remote schooling experience, for reasons spanning from a lack of digital skills, proper equipment at home, and generally feeling overwhelmed. Some families, however, proactively adapted to the situation by acquiring new devices and learning how to better use digital technology.

Although stressful, the lockdown experience led some children to creatively use digital technology to make up for the lack of social interactions and cope with bad feelings. This was evident with children keeping in touch with friends, attending sports classes online, or even using a smartphone to narrate how they felt in a video diary.

Looking back at these challenging times, both parents and children were extremely glad they were over at the time of the interviews, pointing to the plethora of difficulties that families had to deal with due to COVID-19. It is however important to emphasise that because our data refer to the first lockdown, new research should build on our findings as a starting point to see how things evolved during the following phases of the pandemic, so to understand whether children and parents felt better equipped and more resilient or if challenges and difficulties persisted or even exacerbated.

7. References

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